

Synthesis of 3-Amino-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones. Part-I

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Manuscript received 6 July 1990, revised 25 September 1992, accepted 12 November 1992

Monocyclic β -lactam antibiotics are known to possess good antibacterial properties¹. Simple azetid-2-ones can show other forms of biological activity including inhibition of aspartate oxidase and other enzymes and are versatile intermediates for the synthesis of variety of β -lactam systems. In the present communication, the synthesis of some 3-amino-1,4-diarylazetid-2-one, via the imine/ketone equivalent cycloaddition reaction² is reported.

Veratraldehyde was condensed with *p*-chloroaniline to give 4-chloro-*N*-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methylenebenzenamine (1). The Schiff bases 2–4 were similarly prepared by using *p*-nitroaniline, *p*-toluidine and 2,3-xylidine respectively.

Phthalimidoacetyl chloride prepared³ from phthalic anhydride was treated with the four imines 1–4 in the presence of triethylamine to produce the corresponding four 3-phthalimidoyl 1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones (5–8). Dephthaloylation⁴ of compounds 5–8 using 95% hydrazine afforded the corresponding 3-amino-1,4-diarylazetid-2-ones (9–12). The free amino function in 9 was confirmed by derivatising with *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde to give 3-[(3-nitrophenylmethylene)amino]-4-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)azetid-2-one (13).

The compounds (Table 1) were characterised and confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, uv, ir and nmr spectral data

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal reference.

Substituted-*N*-[(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methylene]benzenamines (1–4): Veratraldehyde (0.1 mol) was refluxed with the appropriate amine (0.1 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) for 45 min. The mixture was then cooled to 10° and the solid separated was recrystallised.

3-Phthalimidoyl-1,4-diarylazetid-2-one (5–8): The appropriate [(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)methylene]benzenamine (1–4; 0.04 mol) and triethylamine (0.02 mol) were dissolved in dry benzene (80 ml). To this mixture, phthaliminoacetyl chloride was added dropwise with stirring for 1.5 h. The mixture was stirred for 1 h when triethylammonium chloride separated, which was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under reduced pres-

sure to get a viscous liquid, which was digested with a mixture of *n*-hexane and diethylether (1 : 1; 3 × 30 ml) to remove any unreacted imine. The resulting solid was digested with ethanol (200 ml) for 1.5 h, then cooled and filtered. The solid was recrystallised from dioxane–H₂O (1 : 1).

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-13

Compd. no.	M.p.* °C	λ_{\max} nm	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ
1	83-84 ^a	328	1 640 (CH=N)	3.91, 3.95 (6H, 2s, OCH ₃), 6.8-7.6 (7H, m, ArH), 8.3 (1H, s, CH=N)
2	141.5-144 ^a (lit.)	360	1 620 (CH=N), 1 500, 1 350 (NO ₂)	—
3	87-89 ^a (lit.)	325	1 620 (CH=N)	2.4 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.95 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 6.8-7.6 (7H, m, ArH), 8.35 (1H, s, CH=N)
4	81.5-83.5 ^a	312	1 640 (CH=N)	2.3 (6H, s, CH ₃), 3.95 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 6.7-7.7 (6H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, s, CH=N)
5	189-191 ^b	241	1 730 (C=O phthalimido), 1 770 (C=O β -lactam)	3.9 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 5.39 (2H, s, C-3, C-4H), 6.8-8 (11H, m, ArH)
6	192-196 ^b	372	1 720 (C=O, phthalimido), 1 780 (C=O, β -lactam), 1 500, 1 350 (NO ₂)	3.8 (6H, 2s, OCH ₃), 5.2 (2H, s, C-3, C-4H), 6.65-7.8 (11H, m, ArH)
7	127-130 ^b	240	1 720 (C=O phthalimido), 1 780 (C=O β -lactam)	2.25 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.8 (6H, 2s, OCH ₃), 5.2 (2H, s, C-3, C-4H), 6.8-8.0 (11H, m, ArH)
8	163-165 ^b	283	1 720 (C=O phthalimido), 1 760 (C=O β -lactam)	2.3, 2.4 (6H, 2s, CH ₃), 3.86 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 5.43 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, C-3H), 5.6 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 2 Hz, C-4H), 6.8-8.0 (10H, m, ArH)
9	106-108 ^c	241	1 765 (C=O β -lactam), 3 300-3 400 (N-H)	3.7 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.4 (2H, b, NH ₂), 5.3 (2H, s, C-3, C-4H), 6.6-7.6 (7H, m, ArH)
10	125-127 ^c	303, 358	1 760 (C=O, β -lactam), 1 500, 1 350 (NO ₂), 3 300-3 100 (NH)	3.1-3.6 (2H, b, NH ₂), 3.95 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 5.5 (1H, d, C-3H), 5.8 (1H, d, C-3H), 7.0-7.6 (7H, m, ArH)
11	82-84 ^c	240	1 780 (C=O β -lactam), 3 300-3 000 (NH)	1.0-1.3 (2H, b, NH ₂), 2.15 (3H, s, CH ₃), 3.8 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (1H, s, C-4H), 5.2 (1H, s, C-3H), 6.7-7.6 (7H, m, ArH)

12	95-97 ^c	278.2	3 380-3 000 (NH), 1 775 (C=O β -lactam)	2.1-3.1 (2H, b, NH ₂), 2.33 (6H, s, CH ₃), 3.86 (6H, s, OCH ₃), 4.85 (2H, s, C-3, C-4H), 6.9-7.2 (6H, m, ArH)
13	152-154 ^d	243	1 640 (CH=N), 1 760 (C=O β -lactam)	—

*Solvent for crystallisation: ^aEtOH, ^bDioxane-H₂O (1:1), ^cC₆H₆, ^dMeOH. **In MeOH. Mass spectra of compounds: 4 *m/z* 269 (100% *M*⁺, base); 8 *m/z* 456 (*M*⁺, 309 (100% base); 12 *m/z* 326 (*M*⁺), 270 (100% base).

3-Amino-1,4-diarylazetidines (9-12): The appropriate 3-phthalimidoyl-1,4-diarylazetidines (5-8; 0.001 mol) was stirred with a methanolic solution of 90% hydrazine (0.004 mol) in methylene chloride (50 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. The precipitated phthalhydrazide was filtered. The filtrate was washed with water (3 × 50 ml) and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The methylene chloride was evaporated to give solid residue which was triturated with ether (60 ml). Evaporation of the ether gave the product which was recrystallised from benzene.

3-[(3-Nitrophenyl methylene) amine]-4-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-azetidines (13): A mixture of 3-amino-4-(3,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)azetidines (0.001 mol, 0.332 g) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.001 mol, 0.151 g) was dissolved in methanol (10 ml), then stirred for 1 h and left overnight at room temperature. The solid separated was crystallised from methanol (0.385 g), m.p. 152-54°.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Prof. R. D' Silva, Head of the Chemistry Department, for his keen interest and encouragement. They also thank Dr. R. P. Telange, Boots (India) Ltd., Bombay, for spectral and elemental analyses.

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